

INNOMICS®

An Introduction v.1

Innomantra Consulting

INNOMICS®

Innomics is played by 3-4 players with

- 1-2 players playing the role of 'Banker'
- 2-3 players playing the role of Entrepreneur

Banker: The banker starts of with is an asset base of 10,000 M, and his objective is to create maximum returns for the Bank.

The Banker's activities

1. Auctioning Land
 - a. The Banker is able to procure land at face value and auction in to Entrepreneurs
2. Auctioning product licenses
3. Providing loans for the Entrepreneurs
4. Buying equity
5. Receiving commission on sales of Entrepreneurs
6. Maintain bank accounts for the Entrepreneurs

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Innomics is played by 3-4 players with

- 1-2 players playing the role of 'Banker'
- 2-3 players playing the role of Entrepreneur

The Entrepreneur: makes profits by selling products in the market.

The Entrepreneurs' activities

1. Buying land
 - a. Can be used to set up HQ, factories, R&D Centre, Marketing unit
2. Produce and sell products
3. Patent products
4. Trademark brand
5. File law suit
6. Take insurance
7. Take loan from bank

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The Innomics board has 64 squares

- 36 blue squares of property (blue with face value indicated)
- 28 outer squares which indicate the current position of the game

00	01	02	03	04	05	06	07
27							08
26	100	100	100	100	100	100	09
25	100	200	200	200	200	100	10
24	100	200	500	500	200	100	11
23	100	200	200	200	200	100	12
22	100	100	100	100	100	100	13
21	20	19	18	17	16	15	14

- 00-Start, Go to Market
- 01-Equity Offer
- 02-Land Auction
- 03-Product License
- 04-Loan Offer
- 05-Invest
- 06-Land Auction
- 07- Go to Market
- 08-Copy
- 09-Produce License
- 10-Equity Offer
- 11-Land Auction
- 12-Invest
- 13-Loan Offer
- 14- Go to Market
- 15-Court
- 16-Equity Offer
- 17-Exchange
- 18-Trademark Office
- 19-Invest
- 20-Patent Office
- 21- Go to Market
- 22-Loan Offer
- 23-Insurance
- 24-Land Auction
- 25-Trademark Office
- 26-Invest
- 27-Patent Office

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Property squares can be used to construct

1. Product HQ
2. Factory
3. R&D Centre
4. Marketing Centre
5. Housing

00	01	02	03	04	05	06	07
27	100 100 100 100 100 100						08
26	100 200 200 200 200 100						09
25	100 200 500 500 200 100						10
24	100 200 500 500 200 100						11
23	100 200 200 200 200 100						12
22	100 100 100 100 100 100						13
21	20	19	18	17	16	15	14

PROPERTY SQUARES

Property Square Rules

1. The property has a face value indicated, and is purchased by the Banker at this price. However the banker can auction this at a higher price to the Entrepreneur (See Land Auction)
2. The HQ of the product can be set up only after a product license is received.
 1. R&D centre and Marketing centers must lie adjacent to the product HQ, a
 2. Factory must lie adjacent to HQ, or another factory of the property
3. Property deed is sold, after every auction, and a property wall can be made over the bought property

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The positions squares number 28, and indicate the position of the game

Position Square

1. All players (Entrepreneurs and Bankers) take turn throwing the die
2. The game starts at 00, and moves around clockwise

POSITION SQUARE

- 00-Start, Go to Market
- 01-Equity Offer
- 02-Land Auction
- 03-Product License
- 04-Loan Offer
- 05-Invest
- 06-Land Auction
- 07- Go to Market
- 08-Copy
- 09-Produce License
- 10-Equity Offer
- 11-Land Auction
- 12-Invest
- 13-Loan Offer
- 14- Go to Market
- 15-Court
- 16-Equity Offer
- 17-Exchange
- 18-Trademark Office
- 19-Invest
- 20-Patent Office
- 21- Go to Market
- 22-Loan Offer
- 23-Insurance
- 24-Land Auction
- 25-Trademark Office
- 26-Invest
- 27-Patent Office

There are 12 kinds of square

1. Go to Market
2. Invest
3. Equity Offer
4. Loan Offer
5. Exchange
6. Land Auction
7. Product License
8. Copy
9. Patent Office
10. Trademark Office
11. Insurance
12. Court

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GO TO MARKET

INVEST

EQUITY OFFER

LOAN OFFER

EXCHANGE

LAND AUCTION

PRODUCT LICENSE

COPY

PATENT OFFICE

TRADEMARK OFFICE

INSURANCE

COURT

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License Card

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Go to Market X 4

GO TO MARKET

GO TO MARKET

- Only one kind of product can be sold by a company at a visit to the market
- The demand for any product is printed on the License Card and is in the form of $Q=A - (A/B)P + CPx$
Where,

P is the price the owner can set

Q is the quantity demanded

Px is the price of other good being sold

A: Constant that depends on product & R&D

B: Constant that depends on Marketing & TM

C: Constant that depends on the other product

- The value of A increases when R&D Centre is Setup, and Patent is taken
- The value of B increases when Marketing Unit is set up and Trade-marking is done
- The Cost of the product, mentioned in the product card is subtracted, commission of 1% is paid to bank, and the profits deposited in the company account

Related Topics

[1. License Cards](#)

00							07
	100	100	100	100	100	100	
	100	200	200	200	200	100	
	100	200	500	500	200	100	
	100	200	500	500	200	100	
	100	200	200	200	200	100	
	100	100	100	100	100	100	
21							14

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					05		
	100	100	100	100	100	100	
26	100	200	200	200	200	100	
	100	200	500	500	200	100	
	100	200	500	500	200	100	
	100	200	200	200	200	100	12
	100	100	100	100	100	100	
		19					

Invest x 4

When the game lands on the “Invest” square, the player can choose to build any of the following on the land

1. HQ
2. Factory
3. R&D Centre
4. Marketing Unit
5. Housing Block

HQ: For every product an HQ has to be set up, or an existing HQ should be modified. Only factories contiguous to the Product HQ can make that particular product. R&D and marketing unit should be located in a square adjacent to the HQ

Factory: Each Factory unit can produce and stock 10 units of a product.

R&D Centre: The R&D Centre is focused on improving product design. The benefits of the R&D Centre is immediately seen , as the price that can be charged for a fixed quantity increases. An R&D Centre is a pre-requisite for filing a Patent

Marketing Centre: The R&D Centre is focused on improving product design. The benefits of the R&D Centre is immediately seen , as demand for the product increases for the same price. A marketing Centre is a pre-requisite for filing a Trademark

Housing Blocks : They provide rent on unused land at 10%

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Equity Offer

Here the Bank representing a Private Equity firm offers to buy a part of your company. Depending on the part you sell, a portion of your profits are transferred to the bank

EQUITY OFFER

EQUITY OFFER

The fair rates are provided with the Bank, but this can be negotiated

Equity %	Price
10	2 BV
20	5 BV
30	10 BV

	01						
	100	100	100	100	100	100	
	100	200	200	200	200	100	
	100	200	500	500	200	100	10
	100	200	500	500	200	100	
	100	200	200	200	200	100	
	100	100	100	100	100	100	
					16		

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Exchange

Here the players have the option to trade

1. Real Estate
2. Product Cards

EXCHANGE

EXCHANGE

Export Deal Card

Fire in Factory

	100	100	100	100	100	100	
	100	200	200	200	200	100	
	100	200	500	500	200	100	
	100	200	500	500	200	100	
	100	200	200	200	200	100	
	100	100	100	100	100	100	
				17			

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Land Auction

Here the players have the option to buy land at the auction

Rules

1. The banker holds all the land, purchased at a price called 'Face Value', this price is indicated on the corresponding square
2. The land is auctioned off every time the game reaches 'Land Auction' Square
3. At least one piece of property has to be auctioned every time till the entire area is auctioned off

		02				06	
	100	100	100	100	100	100	
	100	200	200	200	200	100	
	100	200	500	500	200	100	
24	100	200	500	500	200	100	11
	100	200	200	200	200	100	
	100	100	100	100	100	100	

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Product License

License to manufacture the following products can be purchased

1. Red Ice
2. Blue Ice
3. Red Box
4. Blue Box
5. Black Pin
6. Silver Spoon

These six products are auctioned off by the Bank. At least one product must be put up for sale every time the game reaches "Product license Square"

			03				
	100	100	100	100	100	100	
	100	200	200	200	200	100	09
	100	200	500	500	200	100	
	100	200	500	500	200	100	
	100	200	200	200	200	100	
	100	100	100	100	100	100	

- Red ICE and Blue ICE are substitutes
- Red BOX and Blue BOX are substitutes
- Red ICE and Red BOX are complements
- Blue ICE and Blue BOX are complements

If you own Red ICE and Red BOX, you can buy the license to manufacture Red ICE BOX or RED BOX ICE when the game lands on "Product License Square". Similarly If you own Blue ICE and Blue BOX, you can buy the license to manufacture Blue ICE-BOX or Blue BOX ICE when the game lands on "Buy Product License "

If you own Red ICE and Blue ICE, you can buy the license to manufacture Green ICE when the game lands on "Product License Square". Similarly if you own Blue ICE and Blue Box, you can buy the license to manufacture Green Box when the game lands on "Buy Product License" square

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Copy

The Copy Cat card allows the holder to copy a competitors product. There are 4 Copy Cards available

1. Copy Card for ICE
2. Copy Card for BOX
3. Copy Card for Red
4. Copy Card for Blue

If a player holds a Copy Card for a product, the profits made by a competitor on the product has to be split 50-50 and shared with the Copy Cat holder

	100	100	100	100	100	100	08
	100	200	200	200	200	100	
	100	200	500	500	200	100	
	100	200	500	500	200	100	
	100	200	200	200	200	100	
	100	100	100	100	100	100	

A Copy Cat Holder can be sued by a genuine license holder at the Court. This is allowed even if the holder has not exercised the card. The Copy Cat Holder has to throw a 'Six' to win the case, otherwise the plaintiff wins damages. If the CCC holder, on throwing a six, receives damages for wrongful lawsuit.

The Copy Cat Card can be returned at anytime to the bank. Then case cannot be filed against the player, even if the card has been exercised.

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Patent Office

A patent can be filed by a player for any of the products

1. An ICE
2. A Box
3. An ICE BOX

Once a patent is filed, the player has to throw an even to see if the patent is received

If two players with same product ("ICE"), file for the same time, the first player to obtain the card reserves to file first

A player can continue producing a product, even if the patent right has been awarded to the competitor. But case-can be filed in the court against damages. The case is decided the same way as for a CCC violation

PATENT OFFICE

PATENT OFFICE

27	100	100	100	100	100	100	
	100	200	200	200	200	100	
	100	200	500	500	200	100	
	100	200	500	500	200	100	
	100	200	200	200	200	100	
	100	100	100	100	100	100	
	20						

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Trademark Office

A trademark can be filed by a player for any of the names, if he holds a license for a product with the name

1. Red
2. Blue
3. Green

Once a trademark is filed, the player has to throw an even to see if the patent is received

If two players holding cards with same name ("RED"), file for the same time, the first player to obtain the card reserves the right to file first

A player can continue producing a product, even if the trademark has been awarded to the competitor. But case- can be filed in the court against damages. The case is decided the same way as for a CCC violation

	100	100	100	100	100	100	
	100	200	200	200	200	100	
25	100	200	500	500	200	100	
	100	200	500	500	200	100	
	100	200	200	200	200	100	
	100	100	100	100	100	100	
			18				

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Insurance

The Players can file insurance against the following

1. Factory Fire
2. Product Failure
3. Loss of Product Patent
4. Loss of Trademark
5. Wrongful Damages

The amount to be paid is 10% of total value

INSURANCE

INSURANCE

	100	100	100	100	100	100	
	100	200	200	200	200	100	
	100	200	500	500	200	100	
	100	200	500	500	200	100	
23	100	200	200	200	200	100	
	100	100	100	100	100	100	

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Court

The court decides on the following

1. Imitation of Products: See Copy cat card
2. Patent Violation
3. Trademark Violation

COURT

COURT

	100	100	100	100	100	100	
	100	200	200	200	200	100	
	100	200	500	500	200	100	
	100	200	500	500	200	100	
	100	200	200	200	200	100	
	100	100	100	100	100	100	
						15	

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GO TO MARKET

INVEST

EQUITY OFFER

LOAN OFFER

EXCHANGE

LAND AUCTION

PRODUCT LICENSE

COPY

PATENT OFFICE

TRADEMARK OFFICE

INSURANCE

COURT

Red ICE

BLACK PIN

$Q=200; P=B$

	Init	MC	TM
B	2	3	4

If $A=10$, and $B=30$; for Price $P = 10$, and price of complement of $P_c=10$

BLACK PIN

PRODUCT LICENSE

Face Value 100 M

Cost of RM 1 M

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SILVER SPOON

Q=A; P=20

	Init	R&D C	Patent
A	10	15	20

If A=10, and B=30; for Price P = 10, and price of complement of Pc=10

SILVER SPOON

PRODUCT LICENSE

Face Value 100 M

Cost of RM 10 M

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Red ICE

Red ICE

$$Q = A - (A/B)P + CPx$$

A	Init	R&D C	Patent
	10	20	30
B	Init	MC	TM
	40	80	90
C	RB	BB	BI
	5	2	-5

If A=10, and B=30; for Price P = 10, and price of complement of Pc=10

Red ICE

PRODUCT LICENSE

Face Value 100 M

Cost of RM 1 M

Red BOX

$$Q = A - (A/B)P + CPx$$

A	Init	R&D C	Patent
	40	80	90
B	Init	MC	TM
	10	20	30
C	RI	BI	BB
	5	2	-5

If A=10, and B=30; for Price P = 10, and price of complement of Pc=10

Red BOX

PRODUCT LICENSE

Face Value 100 M

Cost of RM 1 M

BLUE ICE

$$Q = A - (A/B)P + CPx$$

A	Init	R&D C	Patent
	20	40	60
B	Init	MC	TM
	30	60	90
C	BB	RB	RI
	5	2	-5

If A=10, and B=30; for Price P = 10, and price of complement of Pc=10

BLUE ICE

PRODUCT LICENSE

Face Value 100 M

Cost of RM 1 M

BLUE BOX

$$Q = A - (A/B)P + CPx$$

A	Init	R&D C	Patent
	30	60	90
B	Init	MC	TM
	20	40	60
C	BI	RI	BB
	5	2	-5

If A=10, and B=30; for Price P = 10, and price of complement of Pc=10

BLUE BOX

PRODUCT LICENSE

Face Value 100 M

Cost of RM 1 M

Red ICEBOX

$$Q = A - (A/B)P + CPx$$

	Init	R&D C	Patent
A	200	400	600
	Init	MC	TM
B	200	400	600
	BIB		
C	-20		

If A=10, and B=30; for Price P = 10, and price of complement of Pc=10

Red ICEBOX

PRODUCT LICENSE

Face Value 100 M

Cost of RM 2 M

BLUE ICEBOX

$$Q = A - (A/B)P + CP_x$$

	Init	R&D C	Patent
A	100	500	1000
	Init	MC	TM
B	100	500	1000
	RIB		
C	-20		

If A=10, and B=30; for Price P = 10, and price of complement of Pc=10

BLUE BOXICE

PRODUCT LICENSE

Face Value 100 M

Cost of RM 10 M

Green ICE

$$Q = A - (A/B)P + CPx$$

	Init	R&D C	Patent
A	100	200	300
	Init	MC	TM
B	100	200	300
	GB		
C	10		

If A=10, and B=30; for Price P = 10, and price of complement of Pc=10

Green ICE

PRODUCT LICENSE

Face Value 100 M

Cost of RM 1 M

Green BOX

$$Q = A - (A/B)P + CP_x$$

	Init	R&D C	Patent
A	100	200	500
	Init	MC	TM
B	100	200	500
	GI	BB	BI
C	10		

If A=10, and B=30; for Price P = 10, and price of complement of Pc=10

Green BOX

PRODUCT LICENSE

Face Value 100 M

Cost of RM 5 M

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Green ICEBOX

$$Q = A - (A/B)P + CPx$$

A	Init 1000	R&D C 2000	Patent 5000
B	Init 1000	MC 2000	TM 5000
C			

If A=10, and B=30; for Price P = 10, and price of complement of Pc=10

Green ICEBOX

PRODUCT LICENSE

Face Value 100 M
Cost of RM 1 M

Green BOXICE

$$Q=A - (A/B)P + CPx$$

A	Init 1000	R&D C 2000	Patent 5000
B	Init 1000	MC 2000	TM 5000
C			

If A=10, and B=30; for Price P = 10, and price of complement of Pc=10

Green BOXICE

PRODUCT LICENSE

Face Value 100 M
Cost of RM 1 M

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License Card	Patent Required for Purchase	Face Value
Black Pin	None	100
Silver Spoon	None	100
Red ICE	None	100
Blue ICE	None	100
Red BOX	None	200
Blue BOX	None	200
Red ICEBOX	Red ICE, Red BOX	500
Blue BOXICE	Blue Box, Blue ICE	400
Green ICE	Red ICE, Blue ICE	500
Green BOX	Red BOX, Green BOX	600
Green BOXICE	Red BOXICE, Blue ICE	800
Green ICEBOX	Red ICEBOX, Blue Box	1000